

A View of the Chemical Valley: Waste and Wasting in Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio's "The Outsiders"

Pedro Miguel Carmona Rodríguez (pmcarmo@ull.es)

 0000-0001-8722-3861

Universidad de la Laguna

Abstract: This paper analyses "The Outsiders", the sixth short story included in Canadian Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio's 2023 collection *Reuniting with Strangers*, from the productive juncture at the intersection of environmental and eco-social justice theories. With special attention to the local-international scale of globalisation processes, and the defiance brought to light by the attempt at narrating eco-social violence, it is proposed first that the so-called Anthropogenic Great Acceleration, which chronologically encloses Filipinos' first massive arrivals at Canada, also provides a context in which to weave a critical dialogue between turbo-capitalist ecological disposability and human dispensability within toxic neoliberal power structures. Secondly, it is argued that, within a general context of dynamic wasting relations, the story articulates a general repoliticisation of the current socio-ecological crisis in which a transnational alliance based on sharing and caring reduces power asymmetries and provokes a collapse of the dualities scaffolding concepts like home and outsider to advocate instead their multiscale refiguration.

Keywords: Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio, "The Outsiders", waste and wasting, Filipino Canadian, Canadian literature.

Una panorámica del Valle Químico: Basura y Basurización en "The Outsiders", de Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio

Resumen: Este artículo analiza "The Outsiders", el sexto relato breve que la canadiense Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio incluye en su colección *Reuniting with Strangers* (2023), desde la coyuntura productiva a la que da lugar la intersección de las teorías de justicia ambiental y ecosocial. Con especial atención a la escala local-internacional de los procesos de globalización y al desafío presente en el intento de narrar la violencia ecosocial, se propone en primer lugar que la llamada Gran Aceleración Antropogénica, que enmarca cronológicamente las primeras llegadas masivas de filipinos a Canadá, también proporciona un contexto en el que establecer un diálogo crítico entre la desechabilidad ecológica turbocapitalista y la prescindibilidad humana dentro de las estructuras tóxicas de poder neoliberales. Se sostiene en segundo lugar que, dentro de un contexto general de relaciones dinámicas de basurización, el relato articula una repolitización general de la actual crisis socioecológica en la que una alianza transnacional basada en la distribución y el cuidado reduce las asimetrías de poder y facilita un colapso de dualidades como las que sostienen los conceptos del hogar y lo foráneo, para promover en su lugar una reconfiguración multiescalar.

Palabras clave: Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio, "The Outsiders", basura y basurización, filipino canadienses, literatura canadiense.

1. Introduction

According to Elizabeth M. DeLoughrey, the Anthropocene is characterised by a visible disjunction between knowledge production and its circulation, which may be sutured by allegorical representations given the power of such a trope to feature a dynamic nature in contrast to the future of humans on Earth (3-4). In her view, allegory is well-known for “its embeddedness in history (time), its construction of a world system (space) and its signification practices in which the particular figures for the general and the local for the global” (5). The challenge to render anthropogenic violence representable and readable could in this form match the aim to raise ecological and social awareness in global times of international displacement, resettlement and community transformations.

Critics like Rob Nixon are more precise in their classification of the current times and venture to state that our current moment is that of the Great Acceleration, the second anthropogenic phase, and its “accelerated connectivity” (12), one that has affected the rates of human attention under the effect of “info-whelm[ing]” (Nixon 12). This stage of information excess modifies relations among human community members, their place-based bonds and their self-representations. Drawing on the work by Will Steffen, the Great Acceleration also comprises post-1950s changes in fields as diverse as nation building, shipping, consumption and disposability. For DeLoughrey, these are part and parcel of “the material ‘fall out’ of globalization” and involve “a recognition of a ‘disembedding’ of the human from place, in relation not just to the mobility of circuits of capital and culture, but also to the planet itself” (27).

In opposition to DeLoughrey and Nixon, historian Marco Armiero differentiates our present from the Anthropocene. While every anthropogenic story concedes waste a central role to abound on humans’ capacity to turn the environment into a “gigantic dump” (Armiero 9), the Wasteocene juxtaposes literal and metaphorical residue to investigate the process of wasting, the “socio-ecological relations creating wasted people and wasted places” (Armiero 10; Armiero and De Angelis 356). In taking into consideration these eco-social factors, the Wasteocene draws attention to the presumed neutrality underlying the anthropogenic stage and unveils unequal responsibilities among the

capital-based social groups having the agency to affect the environment, and those affected together with their habitats. In this sense, the Wasteocene “repoliticises the socio-ecological crisis” (Armiero 11) and presents wasting as a process of negotiation between unequal actors. That process is a constituent of the necessary attempt at (re)imagining how personal and communal subjectivities are in an ongoing political transformation in global, present-day times plagued with neocolonial attitudes, neoliberal policies and boundary-making strategies oriented to the containment of difference.

This paper analyses “The Outsiders”, the sixth short story included in Canadian Jennilee Austria-Bonifacio’s 2023 collection *Reuniting with Strangers*, from the productive juncture at the intersection of environmental and eco-social justice theories. Paying special attention to the local-international scale of globalisation processes and the “major challenge” involved to “devise arresting stories” able to reflect a “pervasive but elusive violence of delayed effects” (Nixon 2), one able to simultaneously wastify humans and the environment, it is proposed first that “The Outsiders” intertextualises the anthropogenic Great Acceleration and its socio-economic shifts. This period provides a context for a critical dialogue between turbo-capitalist ecological disposability and human dispensability within toxic neoliberal power structures. Secondly, it is argued that, within a general context of dynamic wasting relations, the story articulates a general repoliticisation of the current socio-ecological crisis in which a transnational alliance of sharing and caring reduces power asymmetries and provokes a collapse of the dualities underlying concepts such as home and outsider to propose in turn their multiscalar reconfiguration.

Reuniting with Strangers interweaves nine seemingly independent stories revolving around the breach and reunion of Filipino families in the context of a migratory passage to Canada. Under the improbable name of Monolith, a child diagnosed with a severe autistic grade appears in all of them, sometimes centrally, and some others, tangentially, as it is the case in “The Outsiders”. Monolith’s silent presence raises some pertinent questions on his role as a catalyst of structural and communal cohesion in the collection. *The Oxford English Dictionary* defines a monolith as a “single block of stone, esp. a large one shaped (frequently in prehistoric times) into a pillar or monument” (“Monolith” n. p.), a

definition that assembles connotations such as sturdiness, support or common origin out of a single mother stone, which bring Monolith to mind as a commemorating emblem of the Filipino community grappling with DeLoughrey's "disembedding" from place. Monolith, like most of the characters in the collection, is both inheritor and protagonist of the Wasteocene, "a planetary phenomenon", which materialises on "particular bodies, ecologies and stories" (Armiero 31), tainting them all with a residual aura.

As evidence of the connectivity provided by the (post-) Great Acceleration within the frames of a disjunctive neo-imperialist, neoliberal Canadianness, *The Canadian Encyclopedia* online dates the first arrivals of Filipinos as early as the nineteenth century and the proliferation of communities from the 1960s on to presently reach almost one million members and become the most numerous of the Southeast Asian Canadian groups (Laquian n. p.). Whereas large unemployment rates and overpopulation are given as propellers for leaving the Philippines, Canada first sponsored international hosting initiatives like the Caregiver Programme (1982–91), which mostly fuelled the immigration of women from the islands, and thus feminised caregiving, and later encouraged the reunification of families. As a matter of fact, Filipinos arriving in Canada go "first in the independent immigrants category" (Laquian n. p.), their current rate of desirability constructed on their qualified aptitude to contribute to the receptor's society and economy. *Reuniting with Strangers* is imbricated in a "regime of disposability" (DeLoughrey 100), setting aptitude and desirability rates against the wastification of Filipino workers, whose residual, low-waged jobs and the hard, living conditions of their transcontinental resettling are ingrained within a neo-imperialist vested sponsorship.

"The Outsiders" presents readers with a double structure whose conflictual halves contradict and supplement each other, toying with a dualist thinking separated by generations, geography and cultures, and an unlikely eventual reconciliation of views. On the one hand, Canadian-born Avril's first-person narration looks back to reach the present. Both her parents, former petrochemical workers settled in Sarnia in the 1970s, died of cancer, while her younger sibling Paulo left for Toronto. Avril's resentment is firstly projected onto Paulo for leaving their parents' home. While she had to become an underage

bar worker to contribute to the family's economy, he was pampered to only focus on the pursuit of his degree and career as a nurse. Avril's bitterness is also directed to her relatives in the Philippines, the recipients of periodical remittances from her parents. The family in Taguig, situated in Metropolitan Manila, is headed by her uncle Edmond, who requested endless payments to afford a remodelled house where Avril's parents were talked into retiring and resuming family life. Neither survived to return to Manila, and instead their money has provided Edmond with a comfortable life. His wife Manuela, in a late wave of Filipino immigration, left for Canada as a caregiver, and in the present time of the story is now ready to bring her offspring to the country: fifteen-year-old Edman and his sister Monela, aged seventeen. That is the moment when, via Paulo, Edmond and Manuela ask Avril, who is now office admin staff, to share her house with them. Avril has grown up a loner, and thus cohabitation proves tough and family bonds meaningless to her.

On the other hand, the second part of the narrative accommodates Monela's first-person perceptions as she documents her early landing in Canada. Her disappointment with her new life in Sarnia poses a stark contrast with her recent past in pleasant and advanced Taguig. Monela demystifies the dream of a Canadian education as the only way to progress and destabilises the ossified representation of things Filipino that Avril inherited from her parents and preserved most of her life. Monela's decision to return to Manila and to Edmond pinpoint Sarnia as far from the ultimate end of her life journey: "Sarnia isn't my final destination" (Austria-Bonifacio 122), she resolutely states as an opening to the future. "The Outsiders" displays a complex dual temporality that looks back and forth, from the past of the Filipino Canadians in Sarnia and to the future, to entertain the viability of a return to the archipelago. Such a perspective is darkened by the durability of chemicals in living beings and habitats, and their transportability, and marks the globality of risk society and its future orientation with "chemical and toxicological contamination", as Molly Wallace holds, determining a transition from the first to the second modernity of global risk (12).

Significantly, *The Canadian Encyclopedia* closes its entry for "Filipino Canadians" by recalling how fluent bilateral relations were jeopardised in 2019, when it was revealed that some Canadian "containers full of

waste were stuck in the Philippines since 2013–14” (Laquian n. p.). While Canada insisted on their “recyclable” content, the Philippines urged their repatriation to Canada, and it was Canada that finally returned the containers home (Laquian n. p.). However, the incident rekindled the controversy raised in 1991, when chief economist of the International Bank Lawrence Summers, in a memo to his institution, put forward hauling the toxic debris of the industrialised North to less-developed African countries, which he later dismissed as his parody of neoliberal strategies of waste disposal (66; see DeLoughrey 102; see Nixon 1, 3, 17). Summers’s proposal belied much of a neo-imperialist distribution of the globe with economic superpowers that, situated mainly in the northern regions of the planet, wastify the less developed southern countries, and what is more, an unequal “global risk distribution”, as Wallace affirms, one with “some benefiting from others’ losses; some able to shield themselves from hazard, environmental or otherwise”, but also a “cosmopolitan spirit of shared hazard” with individuals that “experience their shared condition of “being-at-risk” (12). Wallace concludes that “while the globalized nature of risk can be an opportunity, risks are always represented and experienced unevenly” (22). Unevenness is what the dynamic wasting exposes, while it adumbrates a possibility of renegotiation. Within its scope, we now turn to analysing “The Outsiders” as paradigmatic of a double wastification process nurtured by the Great Acceleration and its multifarious changes to later focus on how sharing and caring reduce social and emotional asymmetries thanks to a multiscalar reconfiguration of duality-based concepts, such as home and outsider.

2. Sarn-hole: Wasting People and Places

In “The Outsiders”, the enmeshing of neo-imperialist neoliberal state practices affect Filipinos and one of the places where their community resettled massively, Sarnia, in southwest Ontario. The unceded territories of the Aamjiwnaang First Nation or Chippewas are now dotted with refineries and oil industry plants, a living testimony of how settler colonialist extractivism affects the environment and dwelling species, in a complete modification of habitats and strategies of survival to eventually impose on their “vernacular landscape” an “official” one, which “writes the land in a bureaucratic, externalizing, and extraction-

driven manner” (Nixon 17). Early Indigenous communities were deteriorated, displaced or extinguished, their existence inflected by the double sense of waste, as loss and detritus. In the area, settler colonialism turned them into “disposable people” (Nixon 4), who preceded a later repopulation with Europeans, and in the middle and late twentieth century, with a large volume of Filipino immigrants. The Sarnia area has often been reported as being one of the most polluted in Canada and with high rates of cancer (MacDonald n. p.), making it difficult to overlook a connection between the cheap accommodation deriving from toxicity and the settlement of Filipinos there. As Avril soon states at the beginning of “The Outsiders”, “we [...] know that without the Chemical Valley, we wouldn’t have our three-bedroom houses; our trucks and cars; our education; our entire damn lives” (108). “Chemical and radiological violence is driven inward”, Nixon says, “somatised into cellular dramas of mutation that particularly in the bodies of the poor remain largely unobserved, undiagnosed, and untreated” (6). Radiological violence has preyed on the bodies of the Filipino community and made Sarnia inhospitable. Imbibed by this reality, “The Outsiders” unfolds a double wastification of people and place, triggered from the state and the community, at local and international levels, which reverses the clichéd identification of Canada and the Philippines with a “garden” and a “dump” (Armiero 10), respectively.

In the story, Sarnia is a post-industrial geography whose toxicity replicates Cynthia Deitering’s “riskscape” (200) and Lawrence Buell’s “betrayed Eden” (647). It is, in other words, an enclave that thanks to human vicious extractivism is not “useful” anymore but “harmful” (Deitering 200). For nearly two centuries, Sarnia has been the object of a gradual degradation that contravenes the traditional connotations of any violent act as momentous, spectacular and sudden. Instead, it falls within the scope of Rob Nixon’s slow violence, namely, a man-made, gradual aggression of long-lasting sequels, erosive and hardly visual, but “incremental and accretive” (2), wasting human bodies and the place of their dwelling.

Between its blooming past in the 1990s and its disgruntled present of bankrupt business and ramshackle edifices, Avril’s pride for being a local goes hand in hand with the decline of Sarn-hole, which is how townspeople refer to Sarnia, since “we don’t tolerate disrespect”

(108). The story rapidly forges a cause-effect relation between industry, cancer rates and the community's decreasing activity in town, since "as the titas and titos died of cancer", Avril asserts, "the only thing that brought our community together was funerals" (109). Unlike most of her fellows, Avril stays in town to pay homage to her parents' sacrifice by preserving their legacy. That seems to be what sparks a conflict with her own brother. For her, those deserting Sarnia, like Paulo, were resorting to "sob stories about Cancer Valley to get [themselves] a free-ride scholarship outta here" (110).

As a product of the anthropogenic Great Acceleration, "The Outsiders" relies on a settler-based, local turbo-capitalist exploitation of resources to reach exhaustion. First, oil extraction and its refinement have polluted Sarnia: "We have to put up with loud-ass emergency warning siren tests every Monday at 12:30 sharp" (108), Avril warns. Even so, locals would drive visitors for a sightseeing tour at dusk "when all the smokestacks were lit up against the night sky, the emissions glowing neon under the flare" (109). At that time, the question "looks just like Vegas, don't it?" (109) was launched, and if visitors hesitated, car windows would be opened for them to breathe "the burning fumes" (109), just for a second before, terrified of being intoxicated, they confirmed "it's beautiful" (109), followed by the shutting up of car windows.

This visible and unbreathable decimation of local Sarnia in the story is paired with international transformations in Filipino nation-building processes, consumption and disposability of human and material resources. While the bilateral programme Caregiver fractured community and family ties, it also produced a controlled displacement of Filipino labour force and a disconnection from place and homeland; it also was a repository of qualified economical workers that escaped the unemployment and overpopulation of the Philippines. In February 2025, the Government of Canada website still announced in its Immigration/Citizenship section what seemed to be the remaining echoes of that early wastification: "If you don't meet the requirements for permanent residence you may be able to work temporarily as a caregiver" ("Government of Canada" n. p.), which offers a relaxation of entry and hosting policies in turn for specialised caregiving work. As Zygmunt Bauman states, economic migrants share with asylum seekers

their “global origin”, and their “contribut[ion] to a stalemate state of affairs”, helping states in their reaffirmation of borders, from their role as the “waste of globalization” (58). In this sense, *the outsiders* may convey not only a reference to newcomers in Sarnia or any other town community, but also to anyone walled off by the state in conditions different from the exceptional permeability of its borders that Filipino workers were presented with. Avril’s unnamed parents in the story reflect the early Filipino migration, whose conditions were not as benevolent as those in practice for their descendants and were therefore much closer to residual citizens to whom Bauman refers as “human waste”. For him, “the production of ‘human waste’, or more correctly ‘wasted humans’” includes “the ‘excessive’ and ‘redundant’, ([...] those who either could not or were not wished to be recognized or allowed to stay)”, and “is a by-product of modernization, and an outcome of modernity” (5).

Globalisation and its modern and free circulation of capital has also brought the Philippines territorial speculation, trends of consumerism and international tourism, creating an uneven juxtaposition of local and international landscapes as a result (Appadurai 33). In Monela’s description, Taguig has passed from being a former fishing village to “the pride of Metro Manila” (124), as “developers turned the area around us into a million luxury condos and designer shops” (122). In her own family, as she reveals, Edmond “respectfully rejected all of the developers’ offers, knowing that our land would be worth more money year after year” (119). In the present time of the “the Outsiders”, the Philippines and Canada then swap places with Taguig and Sarnia as landfill and heaven, two concepts destabilised in the passage across the Pacific that the discourse of globality brings about in the story, through its exploitation of a tensile flexibility of cultural, economic, political or environmental factors to finally render borders redundant (Steger 9).

Despite the generational gap setting them apart, first-wave Filipino migrants to Canada, like Avril’s parents, just as those in a second wave, like Manuela, intended to improve their living conditions with a Canadian heaven in mind. Thus, Manuela left first for Shanghai then to Calgary to help her family, since Edmond’s “crappy high school diploma” (115) was not enough to support them all. Likewise, in the past time frame of “The Outsiders”, Avril’s parents fairly contributed to

improving the lives of relatives in Taguig from their Canadian stability: “Paulo and I never had much”, Avril says of her domestic situation, but “back in the Philippines, they need friggin’ everything” (111). Her parents used to spend hours purchasing essential products to send over to Taguig: “Hanes briefs, Always Pads, Centrum vitamins, Band-Aids, Kleenex, Spam and Hereford Corned beef” were packed in cardboard “balikbayan” boxes. As Avril explains, “balik” stands for return and “bayan’ meant ‘the country’, but there was no way in hell that we’d ever be going back” (111). Daily products give way rapidly to second-hand clothes and toys as Avril’s parents’ preferences for regular shipping to the islands once her seventeen-year-old uncle Edmond is known to imminently become a father. For Avril, also seventeen at the time, the perspective is “so trailer trash” (112).

However, there is a turning point in the story as her parents stop sending second-hand goods and, in turn, send new furnishings and money to remodel their family’s old house: “‘Why does the Philippines get new bedsheets when we’ve had the same ones since I was born?’ [...] ‘And how come they get fluffy new towels when ours have holes in them?’” (113), Avril wonders, realising how her family’s consumption and disposal trends have varied. “Why do they get fancy pillows when we’ve got these ghetto flat ones?” (113), she concludes. Her parents’ determination to retire in Manila and found a definitive Taguig home accounts for the beginning of a new era of 24-hour reception to remittance petitions, as the family in Taguig “kept calling to ask for house renovation money like they believed our smokestacks were spewing out hundred-dollar bills” (113). When they became severely ill, moving to Manila was impossible for Avril’s parents, as was keeping them comfortable in their last days, since “all of our comfortable things were on the other side of the world” (114). For Avril, Sarnia is her family’s *home*; the *home* in Taguig that her parents envisioned is where the “effing leeches” (114), those who wasted their lives, are still having the settled life that they sponsored.

Together with the financial exploitation of Avril’s parents from inside the Filipino community, the story draws on a general wastification, playing at times with the enhanced obsolescence of products and their required expendability, from teen Avril’s riding of a “rusty Crappy Tire bike” (113) to her present driving of a “rusty, black truck” (125)

in which the cassette player still works (110). Avril herself seems to be fond of that oldness, but her scruffy appearance rapidly incites Monela's comment to equate it to aging, with special attention to her unsmart attire of "baggy clothes", which is worsened by unmoisturized skin and oily, uncombed hair (121). Sarnia, in turn, sometime a vibrant hub of Filipinos, is now an aged dormant city of scarce commercial activity in Avril's description, with "Value Village" as the most alluring place "where folks donate the crap they don't want so other folks can get it for dirt cheap" (123). The family house cannot escape this atmosphere of decrepitude either, and Monela's attention is rapidly drawn to closets hoarding "old, green Catholic uniforms", not to mention "shelves with outdated encyclopaedias", inside which folded Graval boxes, sometime bookmarks (121), can still be found. Paulo's long study periods were usually taken with the aid of such a medicine normally used against dizziness, like that produced by car or boat displacements. Therefore, a connection between movement, like that of local or transcontinental migration, and knowledge accumulation to contribute to social ascent and stability is inescapable, as also is the association between them and sickness.

In a similar sense, Monela is quick in realising that disease and the town of Sarnia can easily go hand in hand in the Filipino community's recent history. Instead of an impressive "macopa tree", like those back in the Philippines, from her open window, the newcomer girl now sees "a horrific view of smokestacks that belch wispy clouds into the air" (122). Her impressions on how humans are endangered by this wasting of the land are verified by Avril's mother's breast and her father's pancreatic cancers, which add to the many other cases that reduced the community and discouraged living members from continuing in Sarnia. "Sarnia is Cancer Alley", Avril explains to Monela: "lung cancer, colon cancer, pancreatic cancer, you name it and we've had a tito or tita who's died from it" (127). According to her, "after the Dow Refinery was shut down, Dad's only happiness was waiting for the Sting to play so he could scan the crowd at the hockey games and see which of his old coworkers were still alive" (127). Intoxicated bodies and lives in a panorama of perceptible decimation of resources moors them to "a social process through which class, race and gender injustices become embedded into the socio-ecological metabolism producing both gardens and dumps" (10), namely, Armiero's full definition of what wasting involves, the

creation of “socio-ecological relations” (Armiero 10) producing wasted people and places.

In Taguig, however, capital remitted from abroad has definitely created a gardening effect, a general material improvement accompanied by a perceived reality of social ascent. Manuela’s “caregiving remittances” afforded Edmond and his children “a new car, tailored clothes, skin bleaching, hair rebonding treatments” and “the best private schools” (120). Avril’s mother’s “funds”, in turn, let Edmond benefit from “the incredible dollars to pesos exchange rate to pay for an entire renovation of the house” (120), one now exhibiting “design features that made us look like mysterious old money”. Yet “air-conditioning and hot water and a new roof” were followed by “a taste for imported goods”, these ranging from “hand-painted Portuguese floor tiles” and “a hand-carved Indonesian dining table” to “a Japanese toilet with all the fancy buttons”, and finally “private English tutors” for Edman and Monela to acquire “the foreign accent that every Filipino coveted so much” (120). Tagalog was not spoken any longer and they easily passed as “balikbayans visiting from abroad” (120). Hoarding money for them runs parallel to the discarding of all things Filipino and the accumulation of international influences treasured as a symptom of economic affluence.

The connectivity of the Great Acceleration is fundamental in triggering the purchase and shipping of goods bound to be consumed and/or discarded, or in activating family bonds in the service of that same consumption. Asking for funds incessantly, midnight telephone calls from Taguig distress Avril and her family in the past time of the story, so much so that she switches off her parents’ telephone and leaves her own off the hook, to only hear a “beep-beep-beep” that Avril calls “a sound of peace” (117). In the present of “The Outsiders”, Avril receives via text message Manuela’s request to share the house (114), just before she welcomes her kids with selfies at the airport (119). After hopping off from the Robert Q shuttle in Sarnia, Monela’s first view of the city as a “disappointing place” (118) is endorsed by the size of Avril’s TV set, which is “half the size of the one we have at home” (119). But her brother and Manuela are so excited that they “insist on friending” the cabbie on Facebook (121). If Monela usually texts her father at Taguig (124) so as to persuade him to let her return, Manuela is fond of continually taking selfies and uploading them to Facebook

(119) for Edmond to follow them from the Philippines, and Edman is enthusiastic about “pulling out his phone” to record “how the cars signal to change lanes” or “how Canadians drive like they’re being tested by driving instructors!” (126). Seventeen years earlier, when Monela and Edman were born, Paulo created his first Yahoo email account to be in contact, as he and his sister would be the children’s “ninong” (115)–godfather and godmother. But now conversations are held on Facebook Live (133), and life in Canada is streamed frequently. Monela and Paulo video chat while he is at work caring for a recently arrived child in his nursing centre, a “drowsy” Monolith. Just guessing, Monela believes that Monolith’s silence results from being “overwhelmed” (131), not to say “info-whelmed”, as Rob Nixon defines humans’ usual condition in our current times. This present moment of information excess and disposability, however, may also be the ground for sparking ethical commitment in the form of an antidote to wasting, to which we now turn.

3. Taguig-Sarnia-Taguig: Reuniting Outsiders at Home

The video conference that Monela conducts with Paulo is her attempt at finding a way to soften Avril’s hermetic attitude. It is her impression that Avril, like Monolith, reflects “the longing for company and love and the cry for help, but without the words to ask” (132). In a scene of overconnectivity and accessible communication, the opposite effect is prevailingly produced, as new and more numerous forms of self-representation hardly end disconnection among individuals or community fragmentation, which results in isolation. This contemporary evil that the *reuniting* alluded to in the title of Austria Bonifacio’s collection nuances and presumably counteracts, despite the defamiliarization that displacement and relocation have also brought about, nourishes and is in turn nourished by the wasting ambience that “The Outsiders” recreates. From his peripheral presence in the story, as elsewhere in the collection, Monolith draws attention to the relevance of community bonds, and the need to reformulate them in keeping with premises of diasporic subjectivity. In the representation of that subjectivity, alliances of sharing and caring reduce distance and power asymmetries.

It is not incidental that during Monela's video conference with Paulo, he is backgrounded by posters of "sharing and caring" (129). They enliven the room where he nurses newcomer Monolith, recently transferred from another centre in the Toronto Oakville suburbs (129), where he had been put "on meds" (131) to curb his violent outbursts. The dosage is now being gradually reduced to try other forms to redirect his violence during his adjustment period which is also helped by his mother's moving residence to Toronto's "Little Manila" (131). Paulo's literal caring of the child is complemented by Monela's concern with Avril's loneliness, her bunkerisation to family affect and her excessive attachment to her parents' place and time in Sarnia. As Paulo also affirms, his invitations to visit him in Toronto have always been refused, as if there is "an anchor holding her in place" (130), which impedes her "disembedding" from the enclave of her parent's resettlement and any proximity to the people that worsened their already wasted existence via economic exploitation. "By the end, they didn't have much money left in their savings" (130), Paulo recalls, partially agreeing with Avril's blaming of financial exploitation on their Taguig relatives. Despite the bleak panorama of community fragmentation, exploitative relationships from within the community can be partially dismantled thanks to the founding of emotional alliances among individuals, which Marco Armiero calls "commoning". In contrast to wasting, which "produce[s] profits for a few through othering and extraction", Armiero affirms, commoning "is reproducing communities through sharing and caring" (quoted in Simal-González, "From Waste" 178). Profiting from Avril's parents, their Taguig relatives have extinguished the sense of community, since the unidirectional relation between them has replaced affect with economic advantage.

Armiero's production of communal subjectivities needs be juxtaposed to the panorama of transcontinental displacement that Austria Bonifacio's collection is rooted in. Accordingly, an ethico-political constituent able to refigure unequal social structures is complemented by the liberatory space for the reformulation of transnational subjectivities, enabled by the cross-border circulation of global flows. What Arjun Appadurai terms the coexistence of various (ethno/cultural/financial) landscapes is uprooted and re-routed anywhere (33), creating a scene of traffic and readjustment of cultural subjects. In the service of the precarious survival of ethnicity, such a process relies on

the adaptation and meaningful reuse of cultural signifiers in the age of mass consumption of difference. The otherness mediating the relation Sarnia-Taguig, Avril-Monela, is significantly reduced when community and cultural bonds are rethought and implemented anew.

Historically, Paulo's and Avril's ties to the Philippines have been mostly severed as a reaction to their parents' wasting. For example, both have disremembered and neglected Tagalog and made English their only language. In turn, despite the social prestige attributed to articulate English fluency in the Philippines, Monela retrieves that language in the service of persuading Paulo to visit Avril, which may reignite their relationship. "I haven't used Tagalog since the English tutors rewired my brain", Monela says, "but in this moment, it all comes pouring out. Pasesinya na, Ninong. Kailangan ka ni Ate Avril" (132). Monela's help petition to Paulo seems to also partially spark a reaction from the drowsy Monolith witnessing their conversation: "Monolith blinks his huge eyes open, and his pudgy brown hands reach out to the screen" (132). His attempted hugging of Paulo's phone screen contravenes the distance that the nurse himself set with the community, partially materialised in his resistance to his parents' language. "I can't speak Tagalog [...]", Paulo says, since "after our parents' generation began to die, us kids went our separate ways. [...] I didn't want anything to do with Filipinos anymore" (132). Paulo's way to grapple with his trauma contradicts what Monela proposes, and Monolith emblematises: a return to community bonding despite spatial and temporal distance.

Broadly speaking, in "The Outsiders" that approximation is symbolised by the shifting implications that the term "ninang" acquires for Avril. When Monela is born, Avril grudgingly accepts being her godmother, charging the term with the exploitative aura that she associated with the Taguig family, not to mention the fact that the offer reaches Avril's mother through a "disrespectful" (115) midnight telephone call across the Pacific for her to transmit to her son and daughter. "Mom, tell them I'm not interested in being a godparent to these random kids" (115), she initially responds before later being talked into it by Paulo. The resumption of the term years later in Manuela's text message to Avril asking for room for herself and the kids in the Sarnian house equally triggers Avril's fury. "She has the nerve to call me 'Ninang', she wants me to act like I'm my own cousins' friggin'

godmother?” she yells to later conclude, “I never said yes to that, not now, not ever” (115). And therefore, during most of her stay in Canada, Monela is only permitted to address Avril as “Ate”, meaning “old sister”. Avril blames them all for turning their house into a “war zone” (128), causing a continuous stress to the family and community, derived from urged periodical remittances. “The community got decimated by cancer—that’s not your fault. But the fact that they couldn’t afford the better [*sic*] medical treatments”, Avril complains to Monela, “the fact that all the kids had to clamour for scholarships to get an education—the fact that our parents scrimped and saved just so we could send you the best things, well, that’s your fault” (128).

As Monela empathises with the situation of her Canadian cousins and acknowledges her father’s abusive disrespect, a new perspective for healing Avril and closing the schism of family relations is entertained. When taken on the so-called Sarnia “grand tour” (134) for outsiders, Monela trespasses the border and becomes an *insider*. With her truck windows open, and her eyes “water[ing] in the acrid air” (134), Avril asks the girl if the view reminds her of Las Vegas. However, her response that Sarnia is rather similar to Taguig unsettles Avril’s expectations. Images of an illuminated night skyline, massive shopping malls and wide lanes are recurrent in Monela’s description to fracture Avril’s ossified views of her parents’ homeland as a “backwater village” (134). The revelation that much of the money demanded for years was used to remodel the house in which her parents would live with Edmond brings about a new reality: her Sarnian house “isn’t the only home that you have” (135), Monela reminds her. Avril is then offered the possibility to spend time in Taguig, which opens simultaneously a transoceanic *home* on both sides of the Pacific with relatives on each, and “if you need anything from Canada”, Monela tells, “you can always ask Edman and my ma to send it to you in a balikbayan box” (136), which, replacing exploitation with cooperation, unwrites the former wasting relations predicated on her parents, giving prevalence to a reciprocal exchange over a unidirectional liaison. Monela’s will to return to Taguig and her approach to Avril creates for them a transgenerational nexus that reduces physical and emotional distances, *reuniting* them in bidirectional form, and revitalises family connections, a rekindling evident in Avril’s final permission to be addressed as godmother: “Call me Ninang” (136), Avril corrects Monela when she uses “Ate” instead. This newly coined emotional linkage to

Taguig replaces Edmond's transactional practices with Avril's parents and reconstitutes a community nexus that was severely damaged.

When based on community building and resource sharing, as Armiero holds, commoning interrogates and distorts vertical relations (13; 47), but it also gives visibility to invisible subjects and unmaskes "processes of exploitation and violence" (Armiero and De Angelis 357). Connection building then results in "tracing new circuits of resilient and sustainable production" (Armiero and De Angelis 358). In parallel, commoning places the emphasis on a different form of "politicisation", one that "can happen when you [...] understand that, if the place where you live is a dump", it is because "somebody is using you as a dump" (quoted in Simal-González, "From Waste" 179). Seen through the lenses of commoning, the crossing of the Pacific from Taguig to Sarnia resituates home, but it also refigures community relations in horizontal form. Lastly, it opens a possibility of return, one very remote for Avril at the beginning of the story (111) and rarely contemplated in Monela and Edman's reunion with their mother pages later: "Sarnia is the final Canadian destination" (119), Manuela told them when just arriving in Sarnia town, alluding to the proximity of the city to the US border. Now Taguig-Sarnia-Taguig is also a probable itinerary for reuniting, thanks to the multiscalar processes of global, and no less important, emotional circulation.

As a result of those same processes, the term *outsider* is partially affected in its designation. Being founded on the building of a sturdy border which, through othering, includes and excludes to establish what and who belongs, that boundary appears as porous as the category itself is shifting in the story. Therefore, when the porous border lets selfhood and otherness blend, the presumed other/waste hardly differentiates from self/purity, and residual presences, or "matter out of place" (Armiero 39), transgress their normative location in a wasteocenic system. Consequently, the "borderisation", or containment strategy (Sandten 3), does not quite work in "The Outsiders". Monela herself, on firstly arriving in Avril's house, is prey to that othering mechanism that separates her host from her, her family and community: relying on Avril's disheveled physical appearance, she concludes that "compared to my father, who is always so-together", Avril "looks like a whole other species. It seems impossible that we're related" (121). "The practice of

othering, which is inherent to the colonial project, rests at the heart of any wasting relationship”, Armiero says to then conclude that “the production of waste is connected to the production of the other, and the outside, and of the ‘us’” (2). Drawing on the same mechanism, visitors are outsiders in Sarnia, walled off and unauthorised to refer to it as “Sarn-hole”. In turn, Avril will be “an outsider” in Taguig, “the worst feeling in the world” (136), which, through sharing and caring bonds of homemaking, will be negotiated to grant her admittance. “It’s not so bad when you have someone to give you the grand tour” (136), Monela says, thus realising that caring for her cousin may circumvent any borderisation strategy like the ones implemented by what Armiero terms “wasteocene logic” or “the (re)production of wasted people and places” for the preservation of a “safe and worthy ‘we’” (31). As the present anthropogenic globalisation has imposed its logics of boundary-building and boundary-crossing, these processes used to produce and neglect wasted lives are recurrently brandished to figure out a precarious “we” in a socially and environmentally degraded world (Bauman 97). Commoning, in the form that Armiero defends, is a way to negotiate asymmetry within neoliberal, neo-imperialist frames of vertical relations that wastify people and places, an indebtedness of (post) colonial societies to the project that originated them, still “at the heart of any wasting relationship” in which “othering means to change the ‘nature’ of the other while simultaneously using it to preserve a privilege” (Armiero 2). As “The Outsiders” seems to reflect, these privileges can be drawn on to be recycled and repoliticised to strategically contravene the power of wasting.

4. Conclusions

“The Outsiders” intertextualises the Great Acceleration as one of its most visible influences, making its characters the protagonists and participants of the ground-breaking changes produced in the morphology of the Filipino nation’s migratory passage to Canada, in processes of increasing connectivity and in the relevance given to trends of consumption and the management of detritus. Therefore, the double wastification of place and people that the story displays is also an outcome of the Great Acceleration. Its turbo-capitalist exhaustion of material and human resources paves the way for a transition into a society of global

hazards in which waste disposal is also a source of collective risk in tandem with an uneven power distribution at global levels.

The toxicity of neo-imperialist and neoliberal power frames in the story stems from transnational and local spheres, with a Filipino community on the move showing how its disembedding from place, symptomatic of the Great Acceleration, results in a production of wasted lives in parallel to the production of privilege in our modern civilisation. For Zygmunt Bauman, that civilisation is one “of excess, redundancy, waste and waste disposal” (2004, 97), a bleak panorama which, nevertheless, grounds the plausibility of horizontal ethical alliances of caring and sharing. Apart from exposing the vertical relations that enmesh wasting processes and a repoliticisation of the eco-social crisis of our present times, as Armiero holds, in the story they also enable a refiguration of home and outsider, atavistically moored to dualistic binary formulations, which, when destabilised, may favour a reduction of power asymmetry.

In “The Outsiders” and throughout the collection *Reuniting with Strangers*, Monolith’s allegorical significance, an emblem of the importance of community bonds, also points out the needed refiguration of the Filipino collective in Canada. In that sense, instead of being extremely dependent on its past, or only determined by its future, the diasporic community hankers after the conciliation of both time periods. Likewise, instead of focussing only on its *here* to be oblivious of its *there*, the refigured community that the transgenerational nexus Avril-Monela metonymically embodies, reconciles both time frames and geographies. In that same sense, Monolith’s presence encloses past and present to look forward. It is mandatory now to find ways of expanding the wasting views of the Chemical Valley, of (re)presenting and narrating eco-social violence in multiscalar times of globality.

Notes

¹ CBC’s Best Books of 2023 and longlisted for Canada Reads 2024, *Reuniting with Strangers* is marketed as a “novel” in the front cover of the 2023 Douglas & McIntyre edition. However, the nine narratives composing the book are “a polyphonic chorus” of “interlacing stories” (Maclear n. p.) with recurrent characters that focalise the action from

their own perspective. In his characterisation of the English-Canadian short-story cycle, Gerald Lynch underlines the emphasis on place, community and character as defining traits of a genre, “whole but suspicious of completeness” (96). I would argue for classifying *Reuniting* as a transnational cycle, which playfully toys on the Canadianness of the genre to accommodate Filipino and Filipino-Canadian experience.

² All references to “The Outsiders” are from the 2023 Douglas & McIntyre edition and appear parenthetically indicated by page number only.

³ According to an Earth.org report, the principal four environmental issues in the Philippines are connected to different forms of contamination. Together with sea level rise, air, plastic and marine pollution have capitalised environmentalists’ concern in 2024 (Raji n. p.). The Philippines has been repeatedly pointed out as a “dumping ground” in the global south for northern countries’ hazardous waste. As of 2019, South Korea and Canada had been recurrently denounced for dispatching their trash to the islands (“Philippines” n. p.).

⁴ As Simal-González states in her 2019 pioneering essay on Waste Theory, labels like “global North” do not exactly correspond to geographical coordinates, since New Zealand, for example, its obvious southern location notwithstanding, is enclosed in such a denomination (“The waste” 211), given its status as a developed country.

⁵ Austria-Bonifacio herself is unveiled as Sarnia-born in the personal bio that closes the 2023 Douglas & McIntyre edition of *Reuniting with Strangers* (230). Her story “The Kayaking Lesson” features Lina, a Filipino-Canadian protagonist from Corunna in the area of Sarnia, who relocated in Toronto for university and zealously embarked on kayaking classes. “I was never an outsider” (Austria-Bonifacio 261), Lina says to part ways with her best chums who decided to pass as Chinese to get a better consideration within the Canadian kaleidoscope (see Swan x–xiv). As does “The Outsiders”, “The Kayaking Lesson” plays with the borders that destabilise belonging and its bearing on representation.

⁶ Sarnia has recently been marketed as a clean energy hub (“About the City” n. p.) to transform its toxic image. However, Nixon’s slow violence appears in its history from early on: French settlers from Detroit were the first Europeans to displace the indigenous inhabitants. The 1830s community, The Rapids, was renamed as Port Sarnia in 1836 and Sarnia City in 1914. Oil Springs concentrated the first exploitations of that fossil fuel from 1858 on, and the economic boom was enabled by Canada Steamship Lines in 1913 and Polymer Corporation in 1942. During

the Cold War, the American Government labelled Sarnia a likely target for a Russian nuclear attack given its petrochemical notoriety (“About the City” n. p.).

⁷ Monela’s words can be translated as “sorry, godfather, Ate Avril needs you” (My translation).

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